

DSC INVESTIGATION OF THE INFLUENCE OF CARBON CONTENT ON PEEK CRYSTALLISATION

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1 Introduction

Properties of semi-crystalline thermoplastics are known to be heavily dependent on the degree of crystallinity and therefore on the cooling conditions. This influence of cooling rate on properties has however been observed in structural thermoplastic composites, but the role of carbon fibers on the crystallisation behavior remains poorly known yet although it favors nucleation [1].

Among the semi-crystalline thermoplastics used as composite matrix, PEEK is of major interest due to its high glass transition temperature and mechanical performances. In particular, neat PEEK exhibits an unusual crystallisation behavior resulting in the apparition of two distinct melting peaks on endothermic thermograms [2-4]. The origin of this secondary melting peak is still discussed but many studies tend to show that it would refer to an imperfect crystal structure and/or a low thickness lamellar structure [2,5,6]. This phase is however always taken into account when measuring the degree of crystallinity thanks to Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) traces.

The aim of this study is therefore to assess the influence of “long” carbon fibers on PEEK crystallisation [7]. The crystallisation kinetics, heat of fusion and DSC scans are analyzed and the influence of carbon content on neat PEEK crystallisation behavior is discussed.

2 Materials

Polymer used in this study is a Poly-Ether-Ether-Ketone (PEEK) provided as coarse powder by Victrex (grade 150). Carbon fibers are HR fibers removed from a quadriaxial Non-Crimp Fabric (NCF) used for resin transfer moulding. The removed carbon yarns have been cut in order to obtain 5mm long carbon fibers.

2 Experimental procedures

Aluminum sealed pans have been prepared with 3 to 5mg of PEEK powder and different carbon fibers contents. By controlling the carbon weight ratio, DSC samples of “C/PEEK composites” were thus obtained with 18 to 72%wt of carbon fibers.

DSC measurements have been performed with a Perkin Elmer DSC 8000 apparatus. All the tests have been started by applying a 5min isothermal annealing at 400°C so as to perform crystallisation from a nuclei-free melt. From this molten state, two different cooling conditions have been achieved.

First, isothermal crystallisation have been realized at 305°C during 15min. A constant cooling ramp of 150°C.min⁻¹ was used to cool the samples from melt before and after the isothermal step. Anisothermal crystallisation has also been performed during 20°C.min⁻¹ cooling ramps.

Whatever crystallisation condition used, the melting endotherms were measured during a 10°C.min⁻¹ thermal scan.

3 Main Results

Many different results have been collected on the crystallisation exotherms and melting endotherms thermograms: crystallisation and melting temperatures, heat of fusion and degree of crystallinity, crystallisation kinetics.

Concerning anisothermal crystallisation, Fig 1 shows the crystallisation kinetic for different carbon ratios when subjected to a cooling ramp at 20°C.min⁻¹. The curves exhibit a typical sigmoidal shape which point of inflexion corresponds to the maximum crystallisation kinetic. However, their dissymmetric shape denotes that PEEK has a particular crystallisation behavior that can be related to the apparition of a secondary melting peak on the DSC traces. Moreover, crystallisation kinetic is

increased with increasing the carbon fiber content and nucleation on carbon fiber surface is therefore confirmed.

However, despite its nucleation ability, the presence of carbon fibers is not beneficial for total crystallinity. As plotted in Fig 2, the higher the carbon fiber content is, the lower is the PEEK degree of crystallinity. As a consequence, according to the literature, increasing the fiber content in composite structural part may lead to a drop of the matrix properties.

Fig.1. Influence of carbon fiber content on anisothermal crystallisation kinetic ($20^{\circ}\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ cooling)

Fig.2. Influence of carbon fiber content on PEEK total degree of crystallinity (Anisothermal crystallisation at $20^{\circ}\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ cooling)

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